

Studies in the Cyclooctane Series Part VII. Synthesis of 1-Carboxycyclooctane-1-Acetic Acid and Condensation of its Anhydride with Some Aromatic Compounds

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Cyclooctanone has been condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate to give ethyl cyclooctylidene- α -cyanoacetate; the latter was reacted with potassium cyanide and the potassium salt of the dicyano ester on hydrolysis furnished 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid in only one form. The anhydride of this acid was condensed with benzene, toluene, *o*- and *m*-xylenes, chlorobenzene and anisole in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride to give the corresponding 1-phenacyl and substituted phenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acids. Anisole gave two isomeric keto-acids.

Attempts to prepare benzcyclohexane *spiro* cyclooctane and cyclooctane-1 : 1-dicarboxylic acid were unsuccessful thus leading us to suggest that the cyclooctane ring behaves in a manner different from its lower homologues.

In continuation of our earlier work on the isomerism of cyclohexane¹ and cycloheptane² rings, the present investigation relates to the study of the chemistry of the cyclooctane ring. The work presented in this communication was primarily taken up with the idea of studying the isomerism of the cyclooctane ring under normal conditions by introducing electrical and steric interferences for which the entire series may provide excellent opportunities and further to compare its behaviour with the lower ring systems.

Cyclooctanone was condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate³ to give ethyl cyclooctylidene- α -cyanoacetate (I; $n = 7$) which on treatment with potassium cyanide⁴ yielded the potassium salt of the dicyanoester (II; $n = 7$); its subsequent hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid furnished 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid (III) in only one form and in this behaviour it resembles its lower homologues.

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The anhydride of the acid III was later condensed with benzene, toluene, *o*- and *m*-xylenes and chlorobenzene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride in the cold to yield the corresponding 1-phenacyl and substituted phenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acids (IV; $n = 7$)

- (a) $\text{R} = \text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$
 (b) $\text{R} = \text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_2 = -\text{CH}_3$
 (c) $\text{R} = \text{R}_3 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = -\text{CH}_3$
 (d) $\text{R} = \text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_2 = \text{R}_4 = -\text{CH}_3$
 (e) $\text{R} = \text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_2 = \text{Cl}$
 (f) $\text{R} = \text{R}_1 = \text{R}_3 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$; $\text{R}_2 = -\text{OCH}_3$
 (g) $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{R}_4 = \text{H}$; $\text{R} = -\text{OCH}_3$

Condensation of the anhydride with anisole gave two isomeric acids (IV f, g; $n = 7$); the one having the higher melting point was regarded 1-4'-methoxyphenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid (IV f; $n = 7$) and the other was 1-2'-methoxyphenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid (IV g; $n = 7$).

Reduction of 1-phenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid (IVa; $n = 7$) was attempted both by Clemmensen and Wolff-Kishner methods to obtain 1-phenyl ethyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid (V; $n = 7$), as this acid on cyclisation via its acid chloride may give the cyclic ketone (VI; $n = 7$) which on reduction may finally furnish benzcyclohexane *spiro*-cyclooctane (VII; $n = 7$).

Since the reduction of the keto acid (IV) to the reduced acid (V) could not be achieved, inspite of the varying reaction conditions, the subsequent reactions as envisaged could not be taken up. However, during the course of reaction with amalgamated zinc and hydrochloric acid, a neutral product, believed to be a lactone was obtained^{3,5,6}.

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In view of the above failure of IV to furnish VII via V and VI, the alternate route VIII-IX-X-VII ($n = 7$) was investigated. Following the earlier work of Rothstein and Thorpe⁷, Khuda and Bhattacharya⁸ and Bardhan⁹, the half-acid ester was prepared by refluxing the anhydride of the acid (III) with absolute methanol. The earlier set of workers had obtained methyl-1-carboxy cyclohexane-1-acetate (XI; $n = 5$) by refluxing the anhydride of 1-carboxy cyclohexane-1-acetic acid with absolute methanol though theoretically two half-acid esters (XI and XII; $n = 5$) are possible.

Bardhan (*loc. cit.*) also assigned the structure (XI; $n = 4$) to the half-acid ester obtained by the action of methanol on the anhydride of 1-carboxy cyclopentane-1-acetic acid. The half-acid ester prepared by us was assigned the structure (XI; $n = 7$) in the earlier stages and this was converted into the acid chloride. This was later condensed with benzene and toluene in the hope of getting 1-benzoyl cyclooctane-1-acetic acid (VIII; $n = 7$; Ar = C₆H₅) and 1-*p*-methylbenzoyl cyclooctane-1-acetic acid (VIII; $n = 7$; Ar = *p*-CH₃.C₆H₄) isomeric with 1-phenacyl and 1-*p*-methylphenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acids (IV a and b; $n = 7$) respectively. Our observations revealed that in this case too the keto acids had the structures (IVa and b; $n = 7$) confirmed by m.p. and mixed m.p.; further these acids gave a positive test for the presence of a -CO.CH₂ group by forming the pyrylium salt, thus leading us to believe that the half-acid esters had the structures (XII; $n = 7$) and not XI ($n = 7$) and this was contrary to the observations of earlier workers. This peculiar behaviour of opening of the anhydride ring could only be attributed to the effect of the cyclooctane ring and further work planned had to be stopped at this stage.

Later the synthesis of cyclooctane:1 : 1-dicarboxylic acid (XIV; $n = 7$) from 1-carboxy-cyclooctane-1-acetic acid (III) was attempted according to the method adopted for the preparation of cyclohexane², 4- and 3-methylcyclohexane¹ and cycloheptane²:1 : 1-dicarboxylic acids. The acid (III) was subjected to α -bromination by the Hell-Volhard-Zelinsky method and in spite of varying the reaction conditions such as exposure to U.V. light, decomposing the bromo-acid chloride with anhydrous formic acid or absolute ethanol, 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1- α -bromo acetic acid (XIII; $n = 7$) could not be obtained; everytime the unreacted acid (III) was recovered.

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Further work, here too, had to be stopped and the failure in this reaction also leads us to the conclusion that the cyclooctane ring exerts an influence of its own like of which is not exhibited by cyclohexane and cycloheptane rings.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid.

Ethyl cyclooctylidene- α -cyanoacetate : A mixture of cyclooctanone (12.6 g; 0.1 mole) ethyl cyanoacetate (11.3 g; 0.1 mole), ammonium acetate (0.77 g; 0.1 mol), glacial acetic acid (1.2 g; 0.02 mol) and benzene (60 ml) was heated under reflux in a flask fitted with a modified Dean and Stark constant water separator at 140–60° until no more water separated (8–10 hr). The benzene layer on cooling was washed with water (thrice) and the aqueous portion was again extracted twice with benzene. The combined benzene layer was dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent stripped off; pure ethyl cyclooctylidene- α -cyanoacetate distilled at 158–60°/4 mm, 148–9°/2 mm. (Yield : 18 g; 75%) n_D^{18} 1.5048. (Found : C, 70.3; H, 8.6. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires C, 70.6; H, 8.6%). Potassium salt of the above ester was prepared by adding potassium cyanide (7.8 g; 0.12 mol in water 12 ml) dropwise to a cooled solution of ethyl cyclooctylidene- α -cyanoacetate (18 g; 0.081 mol) in ethanol (80 ml) with continuous stirring. The contents after keeping at room temperature for 48 hrs deposited the *potassium salt* which was filtered, and had m.p. 119° (decomp). (Yield : 12 g; 50.5%).

The above salt (12 g) was hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid on a sand bath for 80 hrs. The solid which had separated was filtered, washed and dried; the filtrate and the washings were extracted with ether, the ethereal solution shaken up with aqueous sodium carbonate (twice). The alkaline extract on acidification deposited a small amount of 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid, m.p. 153–5°.

The alcoholic filtrate on removal of alcohol gave a residue which on hydrolysis further gave some more of the acid. Pure 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid was crystallised from hot water in colourless needles, m.p. 154–5°. (Yield : 8 g; 71%). (Found : C, 56.5; H, 8.6. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$, H_2O , requires C, 56.4; H, 8.5%). Found : Equiv. 116.8 requires 117 dibasic.

Amide : Potassium salt of ethyl 1-cyano-cyclooctane-1- α -cyanoacetate (1 g) was dissolved in water and acidified cautiously with hydrochloric acid; on keeping overnight colourless needles of the amide, m.p. 134–5° (decomp) were obtained.

S-Benzylisothiuronium salt, m.p. 133°; *diamide*, m.p. 183°; *p-toluidide*, m.p. 116°.

Lead, Copper, Calcium, Barium and Cobalt salts of the above acid were prepared in the usual manner and all these were insoluble in hot water.

Ethyl 1-carboethoxy cyclooctane-1-acetate was prepared by refluxing a mixture of 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid (1 g; 0.004 mol), absolute ethanol (5 ml) and dry benzene (10 ml) for 6 hrs and had b.p. 142°/2 mm (Yield : 0.7 g; 63%). (Found : C, 66.5; H, 9.7. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 66.7; H, 9.6%).

Anhydride of 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid : A mixture of 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid (10 g; 0.043 mol) and acetic anhydride (30 ml) was refluxed for 8 hrs and excess of acetic anhydride removed under reduced pressure. The residue on distillation gave pure *anhydride* b.p. 140–2°/2 mm. (Yield : 7.5 g; 87%). (Found : C, 67.4; H, 8.0. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 67.3; H, 8.2%).

1-Carbomethoxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid : A mixture of the above anhydride (5 g; 0.025 mol) and anhydrous methanol (20 ml) was heated under reflux (6 hrs). After removing methanol, the residue had m.p. 89–94° and after two crystallisations from benzene-petrol (40–60°) pure 1-carbomethoxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid was obtained in colourless plates m.p. 102°. (Yield : 3.6 g; 63%). (Found : C, 63.00; H, 8.5. $C_{12}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 63.1; H, 8.7%). (Found : Equiv. 227.4 requires 228 monobasic).

Its *S-benzyl isothiuronium salt* had m.p. 121°. The following derivatives were also prepared :

Anilic acid, white needles m.p. 163°; anil, colourless needles m.p. 139°; *p*-toluidinic acid, needles m.p. 165°; *p*-tolylimide, needles, m.p. 116°; *o*-toluidinic acid, colourless needles, m.p. 131° (decomp.); *o*-tolylimide, colourless needles, m.p. 82°; *m*-toluidinic acid, colourless plates, m.p. 167° (decomp.); *m*-tolylimide, colourless needles, m.p. 127°; α -naphthylimic acid, small needles, m.p. 147° (decomp.); α -naphthylimide, m.p. 119°; β -naphthylimic acid, colourless needles, m.p. 166°; β -naphthylimide, m.p. 154°; *p*-anisidinic acid, small plates, m.p. 154° (decomp.); *o*-anisidinic acid, m.p. 150–1°; *m*-anisidinic acid, shining plates, m.p. 141°; *p*-bromoanilic acid, colourless needles, m.p. 160°; *o*-chloroanilic acid, m.p. 127°; 2 : 4-dichloroanilic acid, needles m.p. 134°; *m*-nitroanilic acid, small shining needles, m.p. 170°; *o*-phenetidinic acid, needles, m.p. 135°; *p*-phenetidinic acid, colourless needles, m.p. 132°.

Synthesis of 1-phenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid : To a solution of the anhydride of 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid (1.96 g; 0.01 mol) in dry benzene (10 ml), powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.67 g; 0.02 mol) was added in lots with cooling and shaking and the contents stored overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was decomposed the following day with ice and hydrochloric acid; the benzene layer was separated and the aqueous portion extracted with benzene (thrice). The combined benzene extracts were washed with water and finally with aqueous sodium carbonate (10%); the alkaline extract on acidification deposited a solid m.p. 142–6°. On crystallisation from dry benzene pure 1-phenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid in small colourless plates melted at 152°; mixed m.p. with 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid m.p. 154° depressed to 128–32°. (Yield : 1.4 g; 56%). (Found : C, 74.2; H, 7.9. $C_{17}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 74.4; H, 8.0%). (Found : Equiv. 273.8 requires 274 monobasic).

It gave a positive test with Borsch's reagent and also gave a pyrylium salt.

1-p-methylphenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid : The anhydride of 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid (1.96 g; 0.01 mol) was dissolved in dry toluene (5 ml) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.67 g; 0.02 mol) added in small lots with constant shaking and cooling. The reaction mixture after keeping overnight at room temperature was decomposed with

ice and hydrochloric acid and excess of toluene removed by steam distillation. The residue was worked up in the usual manner and pure 1-*p*-methylphenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid was crystallised from benzene-petrol (40–60°), m.p. 137°. (Yield : 1.6 g; 51.8%). (Found : C, 74.8; H, 8.1. $C_{13}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 8.3%). (Found : equiv. 287.6 requires 288-monobasic).

1-p-Chlorophenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid : To a solution of the anhydride of 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid (1.96 g; 0.01 mol) in dry monochlorobenzene (5 ml), powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.67 g; 0.02 mol) was added in small lots with continuous shaking and cooling. The reaction mixture after keeping overnight at room temperature was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid, excess of monochlorobenzene removed by steam distillation and the residue worked up in the customary manner. Pure 1-*p*-chlorophenacyl cyclooctane-1-acetic acid distilled at 114°/0.1 mm. (Yield : 0.8 g; 27.3%) n_D^{21} 1.4582. (Found : C, 66.0; H, 7.1. $C_{17}H_{21}O_3Cl$ requires C, 66.1; H, 6.8%). (Found : equiv. 308.0 requires 308.5-monobasic).

Its *S*-benzylisothiuronium salt crystallised from water had m.p. 142°.

1-2' : 4'-Dimethylphenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid : Powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.67 g; 0.02 mol) was added in lots with shaking to a well cooled solution of the anhydride of 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid (1.96 g; 0.01 mol) dissolved in *m*-xylene (5 ml.). The reaction mixture after keeping overnight at room temperature was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and excess of *m*-xylene steam distilled. The residue was extracted with aqueous sodium carbonate and the alkaline extract on acidification deposited a solid m.p. 129–34°; on crystallisation from dry benzene in shining plates pure 1-2' : 4'-dimethylphenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid had m.p. 140°. (Yield : 1.5 g; 50%). (Found : C, 75.0; H, 8.3. $C_{19}H_{26}O_3$ requires C, 75.5; H, 8.6%). (Found : equiv. 301.9 requires 302-monobasic).

Its *S*-benzyl isothiuronium salt crystallised from water had m.p. 128°.

1-3' : 4'-Dimethylphenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid : To a solution of the anhydride of 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid (1.96 g; 0.01 mol) in *o*-xylene (5 ml) powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.67 g; 0.02 mol) was gradually added with cooling and shaking. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temperature, decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid and *o*-xylene steam distilled. The residue was dissolved in aqueous sodium carbonate (10%) and the alkaline extract on acidification deposited a solid m.p. 132–5°; on crystallisation from dry benzene in colourless shining plates pure 1-3' : 4'-dimethylphenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid melted at 142°. (Yield : 1.6 g; 53.3%). (Found : C, 75.6; H, 8.5. $C_{19}H_{26}O_3$ requires C, 75.5; H, 8.6%). (Found : equiv. 301.6 requires 302-monobasic).

Its *S*-benzyl isothiuronium salt crystallised from water had m.p. 126°.

Condensation of the anhydride of 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid with anisole and isolation of the isomeric acids : To a solution of the anhydride of 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid (1.96 g; 0.01 mol) in dry anisole (1.08 g; 0.01 mol) and carbon disulphide (15 ml), powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.67 g; 0.02 mol) was added in small lots during

shaking and cooling. The reaction mixture after keeping overnight at room temperature was freed from carbon disulphide by removing it under reduced pressure and the residue decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. The solid was purified through sodium carbonate and the crude acid melted at 130–42°. (Yield : 1.3 g; 43.3%).

On refluxing with petrol (40–60°) for 4 hrs. the insoluble portion melted at 142–4° which on crystallisation from dry benzene gave pure 1-4'-methoxyphenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid had m.p. 146–7°. (Found : C, 71.2; H, 8.0. $C_{18}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 71.5; H, 7.9%). (Found : equiv. 303.8 requires 304-monobasic).

Its *S*-benzyl isothiuronium salt was crystallised from water and had m.p. 142°.

The petrol soluble fraction on concentration deposited a solid m.p. 130–2°; on crystallisation from petrol (40–60°) in small cubes pure 1-2'-methoxyphenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid had m.p. 132–4°. (Yield : 0.08 g). Mixed m.p. with 1-4'-methoxyphenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid m.p. 146–7° was depressed to 118–26°. (Found : C, 71.4; H, 8.0. $C_{18}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 71.5; H, 7.9%).

Attempted preparation of 1-phenylethyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid : A. 1-Phenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid (1.37 g; 0.005 mol) dissolved in toluene (4 ml) was added to amalgamated mossy zinc (20 g.) in concentrated hydrochloric acid (12 ml) and water (6 ml) and the contents refluxed for 120 hrs. with the addition of extra amounts of hydrochloric acid (2 ml) every six hours. The reaction product on working gave the unchanged keto acid m.p. 154–5°.

B. Reduction was next carried out in absence of water and on working up the reaction mixture, a product insoluble in aqueous sodium carbonate was obtained. On crystallisation from benzene in colourless plates it melted at 117° and was neutral in reaction.

C. 1-Phenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid (4.9 g; 0.018 mol) was dissolved in diethylene glycol (45 ml) sodium hydroxide (3.0 g) added followed by the addition of hydrazine hydrate (7 ml; 80%). After heating and working up the reaction mixture in the usual manner, unchanged 1-phenacyl cyclooctane-1-acetic acid m.p. 154–5° was recovered.

Attempted bromination of 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid : A. Phosphorus pentachloride (6 g; 0.042 mol) was gradually added in small lots to a solution of 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid (4.6 g; 0.02 mol) in dry ether (25 ml) and the contents cooled. After refluxing on a water bath for 6 hrs., ether was recovered and bromine (3.2 g; 0.02 mol) added during 3 hrs. A crystal of iodine was added, the reaction mixture exposed to ultra-violet light for twelve hours and later heated in an oil bath at 50–60° for thirty six hours. The contents were decomposed with formic acid (98–100%) (3 hrs) and the deposited solid after two crystallisations from ethyl acetate-petrol mixture melted at 154–5°, mixed m.p. with 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid was undepressed.

B. In another experiment, the reaction mixture after keeping overnight on crystal of iodine, was exposed to sunlight for two days and on decomposition with formic acid, the unchanged acid m.p. 154–5° was obtained.

C. *Ester method* : The bromoacid chloride complex was decomposed with absolute ethanol and on hydrolysing the ester, 1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetic acid m.p. 154–5° was obtained.

Attempted synthesis of 1-benzoyl cyclooctane-1-acetic acid: Preparation of methyl-1-benzoyl cyclooctane-1-acetate: A mixture of methyl-1-carboxy cyclooctane-1-acetate (1.14 g; 0.005 mol) and thionyl chloride (4 ml) was refluxed for 4 hrs; excess of thionyl chloride removed under reduced pressure and anhydrous benzene added. The contents were cooled in ice and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.46 g; 0.11 mol) added with shaking. After keeping overnight, the reaction mixture was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid; the benzene layer was separated and worked up in the usual manner. After removing benzene, the residue on distillation gave a product which was not the expected methyl 1-benzoyl cyclooctane-1-acetate since it gave the keto acid (IVa; $n = 7$) on hydrolysis and had b.p. 187–9°/3.5 mm. (Yield: 0.8 g; 55.5%). (Found: C, 74.6; H, 8.0. $C_{18}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 8.3%).

The above ester (0.7 g) was refluxed with alcoholic potash (25 ml; 20%) for 6 hrs; alcohol was removed and the residue on acidification deposited a solid which on crystallisation from dry benzene gave a product m.p. 154°. The melting point remained undepressed when mixed with 1-phenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid m.p. 154° obtained by condensing the anhydride of cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid with benzene. This acid also gave the test for a CO-CH₂- group by the formation of the pyrylium salt. Thus it was confirmed that the acid was 1-phenacyl cyclooctane-1-carboxylic acid and not the expected 1-benzoyl cyclooctane-1-acetic acid.

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